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A Teacher? A Mentor? A Friend? – Teacher Mentoring Experience at Tampere University of Technology

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we research a recently set up engineering students' teacher mentoring programme with special interest on teacher mentors' expectations and experiences from the point of view of self-efficacy and motivation. We aim to have an insight in the teacher mentors' met and non-met expectations and see if this has effect on the teacher mentors' motivation and expectations of the outcomes of the mentoring programme. We also examine how beneficial the teacher mentors consider the programme to be to the students and how this is linked to their motivation.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Teacher Mentoring, Transition to University, Student Teacher relationship, Teacher Role

INTRODUCTION

1 TEACHER MENTORING

1.1 Academic faculty as advisors

Is it true that the faculty is uninterested and unskilled academic advisors? This provocative stereotype, mentioned in many articles [1, 2] is still - at least partly – vivid in many universities. In an engineering education setting, this has been seen even as a bigger challenge. Technical universities and the engineering teachers are aware of the importance of soft skills but still priorities hard skills [3, 4] and similarly they find it less interesting and academically challenging to teach those soft practice skills to students than to teach them technical skills [5]. This problem reflects also on teachers' attitudes towards mentoring, where the focus is not on transmitting students' technical knowledge but rather on everything else.

To find out how the university teachers in a technical university evaluate their skills and attitudes towards mentoring, a survey for all teacher mentors at Tampere University of Technology, was executed in the autumn of 2016. In the spring of 2017, the same questionnaire was re-implemented to discover whether there are any changes in their attitudes or in teachers' skills in advising students after they gained experience from being a mentor. In addition to a survey, teachers' opinions were collected in two meetings where teachers exchanged their experiences. The aim was also to recognize whether there are any certain themes that the mentoring teachers find especially challenging in their role as advisors and mentors.

In Finnish universities, the students' transition from a high school to a university has traditionally been aided by a peer tutoring system where a pair of older students meet regularly with a small group of first year students in an informal setting. However, to help the students' integration to the academic community, Tampere University of Technology started a university-wide teacher mentor program where all first year students were appointed a personal teacher mentor. In the planning phase of the teacher mentoring programme, teachers' personal opinions towards mentoring varied widely. Some teachers considered the mentoring programme irrelevant and did not see any benefits for students or for themselves in the process. They considered the students to be too young to integrate into the academic community and thought that first year students are mainly concentrating on their studies and are not interested in developing skills that mentoring offers. On the other hand, some teachers saw this as a good starting point to plant the seed of professional growth in the minds of students and to increase retention rates.

One element, which strongly affects faculty advisors' motivation towards mentoring young students, is teachers' self-efficacy in advising [6, 7]. To enhance the teachers' competence to advise individual students or small student groups, many universities offer trainings on advising students. Somewhat surprisingly, it has turned out that the majority of teacher advisors feel themselves competent regardless of they have received this training on advising or not [6]. At Tampere University of Technology, teachers were able to participate in a voluntary training, which mainly offered skills on how to guide a small group. Our survey revealed that there was no difference in the beliefs of their competence between teachers who had participated in training and those who had not. What was seen instead was that teachers who didn't have experience in mentoring were more confident about their skills than the ones that had been mentors before. The survey also revealed that mentors who weren't sure about their skills and the purpose of mentoring were the most likely to think that the mentoring

is not useful for students. This implies that the role of teacher mentor should have been interpreted better and the aim of the process should have been clarified in more detail.

1.2 The role of teachers in advising and supporting students

In Finnish technical universities, teachers typically have a M.Sc. or a D.Sc. degree in their own field, but little, if any, pedagogical knowledge. Therefore, the idea of a mentoring programme for the first year students raised many questions among teachers when being announced. Many of the teachers felt insecure of their skill to encounter students personally and to communicate with them with topics out of the direct subject discussed during the lectures.

The idea of mentoring itself is not new. Quite the opposite, several articles [8, 9] refer to the idea of mentoring dating back to Homer's *Odyssey* and it is widely used not only in academic settings but also in business context. The advantages of mentoring, are also well known, including increased motivation, more positive self-image and better retention rates among students [8, 10]. In higher education, the terminology related to mentoring, however, is somewhat ambiguous. The terms "mentor" and "faculty advisor" are often presented as synonyms, however a mentoring relationship is claimed to develop only over a longer period of time (National Academy of Sciences 1997). Researchers [8] present definitions of several researchers, where some of them connect mentoring with emotional intimacy with students while others see it more loosely. Regardless of the level of intimacy, researchers [8] also emphasize the uniqueness of each mentorship and the long-time range of it. Both the uniqueness and the long commitment to the relationship may sound somewhat frightening to a teacher with no previous mentoring experience.

It has been noted that better performance in occupational context is related to high self-regulatory efficacy. According to Bandura, who used this concept at the first time in 1977, self-efficacy means person's beliefs about their competence in certain situations by their own performance. [11]. The origins of self-efficacy are stem from social cognitive theory which sees people as active contributor of their lives, not just passive bystanders [12]. This approach has an emphasis on one's thoughts and emotions concerning certain situation and one's behavioural choices. [7]

Self-efficacy is closely linked to motivational, affective, cognitive and decisional factors. It can be seen as the source of motivation related to learning and has an effect on goal setting and persistence in challenging or arduous situations. If the beliefs are low, people tend to give up more easily. [12] Self-efficacy beliefs can enhance person's performance and have an influence also on well-being. The origins of these beliefs are already in childhood, but also experiences over the lifespan affect person's self-efficacy. [11]

In mentoring, self-efficacy is expected to be significant of teacher mentors' success. However, simultaneously it has been recognised, that "it is difficult for mentor teachers to have a sense of self-efficacy if they do not have a clear sense of their roles and responsibilities." [13]

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

At Tampere University of Technology teacher mentoring programme started in the autumn of 2016. Each first year student was appointed a personal teacher mentor and each teacher mentor was guiding a group of about ten students. As part of this new procedure, a survey was implemented to map out mentors' attitudes towards mentoring. The same survey was conducted also in the spring of 2017 to find out if teacher mentors' attitudes and opinions concerning mentoring were changed.

In the first round, in autumn 2016, 52 teacher mentors out of 117 responded the survey. In spring 2017, 31 teacher mentors responded to the survey. The rate of experienced and non-experienced teacher mentors were at same level in both surveys which means that the results are comparable in the frame of this research. The response rate was higher than expected, especially in the first round, but naturally, lacking responses from half of the mentors needs to be acknowledged in the interpretation of the results.

The survey comprised of 8 multiple choice questions and 6 open questions and was very quick to complete. Multiple choice questions offer comparable information on attitudes and open questions deepen the understanding of the results. In both questionnaires, most of the respondents also answered all open questions even if they were not compulsory.

Data was also collected in two open discussion meetings in which teacher mentors met each other and exchanged their experiences. The first meeting was organised in mid-December and the second at the end of March. In these meetings teacher mentors discussed various topics, also the same matters what were covered in survey but in more detail.

2.2 Background information

As background information, teacher mentors were asked if they had had a role as a teacher mentor before, how many students they had in their mentoring group and if they attended any training concentrating on mentoring previously. In both surveys, the ratio between experienced and non-experienced mentors was nearly the same as seen in figure 1.

Fig 1. Ratio between experienced and non-experienced mentors.

The ratio between trained teacher mentors and non-trained teacher mentors did not change significantly either between two studies as seen in figure 2.

Fig 2. Ratio between trained mentors and non-trained mentors.

As the ratios remain nearly the same in both surveys, it is possible to draw conclusions on the attitude changes of teacher mentors.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Teacher mentors' expectations and their experiences

One main aim of the questionnaire was to clarify the expectations and attitudes of teacher mentors to understand better how to support them better in their new role. Teacher mentors were asked to evaluate their self-efficacy, i.e. their skills in interacting with students, guiding studies of the students, supporting professional growth of students, guiding a small group and guiding students to other services. They evaluated their skills on a scale from very poor (1) to very good (4).

In Fig. 3 it is seen that teachers' opinions on how they manage specific skills related to mentoring are not very high, and the opinions do not change significantly after mentoring for one year. In Fig. 4 it is seen that the averages of teachers' self-efficacy towards these skills stayed nearly at the same level when comparing autumn to spring.

Fig.3 How well teacher mentors manage skills in their own opinion

Fig 4. How well teachers' manage the skills in their own opinion

In Fig. 5 it is seen that teachers think very highly of mentoring programme in autumn before the programme was started. They have high expectations towards mentoring and they think that students benefit from the programme. However, after mentoring the students for one academic year, their expectations are lowered and they don't think that students benefit from mentoring that much.

Fig 5. How much do you think students benefit from mentoring

In open answers the same trend was seen. Mentors' thought that in general mentoring programme met their expectations but they do not think that students benefit from the programme. Many mentors also had an idea to give students a direction in their professional growth and this expectation was less often met.

In Table 1 the most common expectations, skills that need developing and challenges in mentoring are listed. These were collected from teacher mentors' open answers. In general the expectations were well met and the challenges and improvements of skills did not vary greatly. Lack of time, scheduling meetings and engaging students were seen challenging before and after a year as a mentor.

Expectations towards mentoring

Autumn 2016	Spring 2017
Get to know the students and learn to understand their world	Met the expectations well in general
Give help and direction in professional growth	Engaging students from the beginning was more difficult than expected
Create a solid base and a good start to studies and	The time needed in mentoring was more than expected
No big expectations	

Challenges

Autumn 2016	Spring 2017
Lack of time	Scheduling
Scheduling	Activate students to participate
Activating the students	Make students to understand the benefits of the mentoring programme
Activate students to participate	
Make students to understand the benefits of the mentoring programme	

Skills that need improving

Autumn 2016	Spring 2017
Guiding students in their studies	Guiding a small group
What topics to cover in the meetings	The topics covered in meetings and the role of the mentor
How to help the professional growth	How to get students to participate more actively

Table 1. Expectations, needs of improvement and challenges of mentoring

The most common expectation that was not met, was the help in the professional growth of the students. However, it seems that teacher mentors had quite different ideas on teacher mentors' roles and therefore also expectations on the help in the professional growth they can facilitate. This is most likely linked to the fact that the beliefs of the benefits of mentoring programme have decreased during the academic year.

As previous research has shown, one problem may be due to the vague role of the mentors and unclear distribution of responsibilities with academic advisors [2]. Thus a clearer role as a mentor and more structured forms of mentoring could enhance mentor's beliefs to one's own skills. It can be asked how the organisation can support to build structures and also affect the mentor's motivational factors.

In general, as seen in the previous research and experiences based on this research, the mentoring is beneficial to both students and the teacher mentors. The problem that lies in the lowered expectations of mentoring in this research may rise from the fact that the benefits are not seen immediately and in recently started mentoring programme these benefits have not realised yet. Despite the lowered expectations, the mentoring programme is seen as a positive action at Tampere University of Technology.

The teachers' motivation and self-efficacy could be increased by social support and reinforcement. It is already known [6] that if faculty members think that they are

adequately prepared to advise students, their levels of self-efficacy increase and the mentors feels more comfortable in their role.

Also previous experience has an influence on person's self-efficational beliefs. The results show that some mentors did not feel secure about their role after the academic year – the experiences, either positive or negative, would be vital to debate and process so that learning could be elicited and the structures for the next year could be seen more explicit from the perspective of single mentor.

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